

Acute Symmetric Arterial Thrombosis of the Four Extremities Associated with Pregnancy: Case Report

Jorge Elpidio Moreno Carranza*¹, Manuel Suarez Ortega², Jesús Fernando Romero Espinosa³, Josué Eder Albavera Gutierrez⁴, Ivonne Alejandra Perales Soto⁴, Álvaro Sebastián Gutierrez Macklis⁵, Alberto Jaramillo Sastré⁶, Jesús Alejandro Olvera Rodríguez⁷, Jorge Manuel Montelongo Hernández⁸, López Barba Jonathan Nadiell⁹, Hannah Naomi Ortega Aranda¹⁰, Eduardo Aldayr Quiroz Diaz¹¹, Fernando Miguel Quiroz Diaz¹¹, Leonardo Esteban Mata Sansores¹², Joselyn Ugalde Rivera¹³, Karen Vanessa García Espinoza¹⁴, Jorge Alan Lara Urbina¹⁵

¹Residente de tercer año del Servicio de Cirugía Plástica y Reconstructiva en el Centro Medico Licenciado Adolfo López Mateos.

²Residente de segundo año del Servicio de Cirugía Plástica y Reconstructiva en el Centro Medico Licenciado Adolfo López Mateos.

³Jefe del Servicio de Cirugía Plástica y Reconstructiva en el Centro Medico Licenciado Adolfo López Mateos.

⁴IMSS HGZ #1 Emilio Varela Luján, Zacatecas, Zacatecas.

⁵Universidad Autónoma de Baja California, Escuela de Ciencias de la Salud, Campus Ensenada, Unidad Valle Dorado.

⁶Facultad de medicina UNAM.

⁷Clínica Hospital Constitución ISSSTE Monterrey, Nuevo León.

⁸Clínica Hospital ISSSTE Gómez Palacio, Durango.

⁹Universidad de Guadalajara.

¹⁰Centro Médico ABC

¹¹Universidad de la Salud del estado de México (UNSA).

¹²Unidad Médica de Alta Especialidad 14 IMSS.

¹³Hospital General de Querétaro.

¹⁴Hospital Regional Tlalnepantla.

¹⁵Hospital General La Perla Nezahualcoyotl.

ABSTRACT

During the normal process of pregnancy, there is a procoagulant state derived from the alteration of all the components of the Virchow Triad. Multiple biochemical and structural changes lead to an increased risk of thromboembolic events. Although venous embolic events are more common, arterial thrombosis generally leads to devastating outcomes. Anticoagulation in pregnant patients has very specific indications, primarily in patients with a history of thromboembolism or poor obstetric history. There are multiple drugs used for venous or arterial thrombosis, some of which are associated with teratogenic effects, the most commonly used being low molecular weight heparin. In cases of valve prosthesis and antiphospholipid syndrome, antiplatelet drugs should be added.

Shock is the main cause of admission and mortality in intensive care units. In the absence of myocardial dysfunction, hypotension is primarily caused by hypovolemia and the physiological inability to self-regulate and adequately perfuse. In these cases, there are guidelines for the use of vasopressors, aimed at maintaining adequate perfusion to essential organs. However, the use of these drugs may be associated with adverse effects, including the possibility of ischemia in some anatomical regions.

In this article, we present the case of a multi-pregnant patient with the presence of several etiopathogenic factors that triggered distal necrosis of all four extremities, requiring amputation.

KEYWORDS: Pregnancy, arterial thromboembolism, Virchow triad, vasopressors, anticoagulants, necrosis, amputation.

ARTICLE DETAILS

Published On:
24 April 2025

Available on:
<https://ijmscrs.com/>

INTRODUCTION

Pregnancy is associated with alterations in the components of the Virchow triad, with a potential procoagulant effect. These changes begin at conception and last until 8 weeks postpartum. There are biochemical changes and alterations in blood flow in the lower extremities specific to pregnant women. An increase in factors VII, VIII, and Von Willebrand factor is observed, while levels of plasminogen activator inhibitor type 1 (PAI-1) quintuple. Levels of PAI-2, produced in the placenta, drastically increase during the third trimester. Thrombin generation markers, such as prothrombin F1+2 and thrombin-antithrombin complexes (TAT), also rise.^{2,3,4,7}

Pregnant women, compared to non-pregnant women, have a higher risk of both arterial and venous thrombosis. During the postpartum period, the risk increases up to 80 times, and in the first 7 days postpartum, the risk is 100 times greater, with 80% being venous and 20% arterial.^{5,6}

Venous thromboembolism is an important cause of maternal morbidity and mortality, occurring in 1 in every 1000 deliveries, with a mortality rate of 1-2%, responsible for 5-10% of all maternal deaths. Of these, 75-80% are deep vein thrombosis, while 20-25% are pulmonary embolisms. Arterial thrombosis associated with pregnancy is a rare entity, but with devastating consequences. Reports indicate the incidence of arterial stroke in pregnant patients is 0.18 per 1000 deliveries, but there are no reports of extremity involvement.^{1,2}

Anticoagulation during pregnancy is not required unless there is a history of thromboembolism or poor obstetric history. Anticoagulants used for the treatment of thrombosis include: oral anticoagulants, unfractionated heparin, low molecular weight heparin, and antiplatelets such as acetylsalicylic acid. Among these, the use of warfarins is associated with embryopathies during the second trimester and maternal-fetal hemorrhage in the third trimester. We will focus on low molecular weight heparin, which is the most commonly used. These drugs are derived from the depolymerization of unfractionated heparin preparations, have a molecular weight of 4,000 to 6,000 daltons, are administered subcutaneously, peak at 4 hours, and have a half-life of 4-5 hours. They do not cross the hemoplacental barrier, so they are not teratogenic. Among antiplatelets, acetylsalicylic acid is considered safe in pregnancy and is indicated in patients with valve prostheses and antiphospholipid syndrome.⁸

Vasopressors, another group of drugs, are essential for maintaining perfusion to vital organs such as the heart and brain in patients who require them. Shock is the main cause of admission and death in intensive care units, with a mortality rate greater than 50%. According to current recommendations, fluid replacement and vasopressor infusion, both guided by hemodynamic monitoring, should be titrated to increase the mean arterial pressure to 65mmHg or higher in patients with a history of systemic hypertension.^{9,12} The use of vasopressors is not without risks and can be associated with ischemia in multiple anatomical regions, including the upper and lower extremities, with an amputation rate of up to 22.2%. However, other factors have been associated with this risk, such as smoking and intravenous drug abuse.^{9,10,11,12}

The aim of this article is to present the case of a patient with multiple etiopathogenic factors that triggered symmetric necrosis of all four extremities, requiring amputation.

CASE REPORT

A 27-year-old woman with a smoking history (2 pack-years) and crystal methamphetamine use, gravida 4, para 1, abortions 2, presented with vaginal bleeding on two occasions over one day, self-medicating with analgesics and nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs without improvement. Upon admission, she showed signs of hypoperfusion with a blood pressure of 54/36 mmHg, mean arterial pressure (MAP) of 41, and heart rate (HR) of 132. She was started on crystalloid solutions with no improvement, so norepinephrine was initiated at a dose of 0.02 mcg/kg/min. A packed red blood cell transfusion was performed, but the blood pressure did not reach target values, so the vasopressor dose was increased, and vasopressin was added at 0.03 IU/kg, along with hydrocortisone. Two hours later, the patient expelled the fetus and underwent a uterine curettage in the obstetric surgery unit with a bleeding of 150cc. She was transferred to the intensive care unit (ICU), where on the second day of hospitalization, she experienced three episodes of pulseless ventricular tachycardia, during which advanced cardiopulmonary resuscitation was performed, and circulation was restored. During these episodes, she reached a maximum dose of 0.80 mcg/kg/min of norepinephrine, 0.08 IU/min of vasopressin, and 0.13 mcg/kg/min of levosimendan.

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Figure 1. Lateral view of the left Hand.

Figure 2. Palm side of the left hand.

Figure 3. Dorsal side of the left Hand.

On the same day, distal cyanosis was observed in all four extremities, with no palpable pulses. An angiology consult was requested, and ischemic changes were found in all four extremities, with absence of capillary refill in all fingers, severe hypothermia, and absence of distal pulses (**Figures 1,2,3,4,5**). A Doppler ultrasound revealed no arterial flow in the proximal thirds of the radial and ulnar arteries in both

upper extremities, and no arterial flow in the proximal thirds of the anterior and posterior tibial arteries in both lower extremities. Based on the physical and imaging findings, the patient was taken to the operating room, where transradial amputations were performed on both upper extremities and infracondylar amputations on both lower extremities.

Figure 4. Dorsal side of the left foot

Figure 5. Dorsal side of the right foot.

DISCUSSION

Despite the significant benefit of vasopressor drugs, they are not without side effects. There are established records of a considerable percentage of amputations due to distal necrosis in the extremities associated with their use, although this is

usually asymmetric and does not affect all four extremities, as seen in our case. This is attributed to the inherent effects of these drugs; however, there are predisposing factors such as smoking and intravenous drug use, the former present in our

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patient. Although she did not use intravenous drugs, she had a history of substance use.

During pregnancy, there are changes specific to the gravid state, including a hypercoagulable state. Additionally, there are immunological pathologies that exacerbate this condition. Although our patient did not have a previously established diagnosis of an immunological disorder, the history of two previous abortions without including the current condition suggests the presence of some autoimmune disease, increasing the risk of thrombosis in this case. All the aforementioned factors—gravid state, suspected autoimmune disease, smoking, substance abuse, and vasopressor use—could justify the severity of the arterial thrombosis in our patient.

CONCLUSION

Despite the life-saving role of vasopressors, their adverse effects can be fatal. In cases like ours, the use of these drugs is crucial to maintain adequate perfusion to vital organs. However, we believe that the fatal outcome in this case was due to the accumulation of multiple predisposing factors that led to the patient's condition. While there are few cases with similar presentations, it is important to consider that patients are not exempt from experiencing this condition and to initiate medical management at the onset of symptoms.

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